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Research Article

Formulation Development And In Vitro Characterization of Orally Disintegrating Tablets for Enhanced Antihypertensive Drug Delivery

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ABSTRACT

Many individuals—including the elderly, young children, and patients with certain medical conditions—face difficulties in swallowing conventional tablets. Fast-disintegrating tablets (FDTs) provide a convenient and patient-friendly alternative, as they dissolve quickly in the mouth without the need for water, thereby improving patient compliance and adherence to prescribed regimens. This study aimed to formulate and evaluate fast-disintegrating tablets of amlodipine, a widely prescribed antihypertensive medication. Tablets were prepared using the direct compression method, with polyvinyl pyrrolidone (4%) employed as a dry binder. Different formulations were developed by varying the proportions of two super disintegrants: sodium starch glycolate (SSG) and crospovidone. Each formulation underwent comprehensive in-vitro evaluation, including tests for hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, disintegration time, drug assay, and dissolution profile. The results demonstrated an inverse relationship between the concentration of super disintegrants and disintegration time. Among all formulations, F8 (containing 5% crospovidone) exhibited the shortest disintegration time of 18 seconds, while F1 (containing 2% SSG) had the longest disintegration time of 1 minute and 5 seconds. All evaluated parameters were within acceptable pharmacopoeial limits. FT-IR spectral analysis confirmed the absence of any chemical interaction between amlodipine and the selected excipients, indicating compatibility of the formulation components. In conclusion, this research highlights the successful development of a fast-disintegrating tablet of amlodipine using the direct compression technique. The combination of crospovidone and SSG, particularly at optimized concentrations, significantly enhanced the disintegration

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performance, offering a promising strategy for improving the administration of antihypertensive therapy in patients with swallowing difficulties.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery is the most preferred and widely used route for systemic administration of drugs, offering convenience and flexibility through a variety of pharmaceutical dosage forms¹. Tablets and capsules are the most common oral dosage forms due to their simplicity and convenience. However, swallowing difficulties in geriatric, pediatric, and psychiatric patients present a significant drawback. To improve compliance, fast-disintegrating tablets (FDTs) have been developed, which rapidly dissolve or disperse in the mouth and can be swallowed easily, potentially bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism²⁻³. Fast-disintegrating tablets are also known by various other names, including orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs), quick-melt or rapid-melt tablets, fast/rapid dissolving tablets (FDTs), mouth-dissolving/disintegrating tablets (MDTs), and porous tablets⁴⁻⁵. Orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) offer advantages over conventional tablets, including rapid fragmentation, quick onset of action, and improved patient compliance, especially for pediatric, geriatric, psychiatric, paralyzed, and bedridden patients. Since ODTs are absorbed through the pre-gastric mucosa within seconds, they help overcome swallowing difficulties⁶⁻⁸. Furthermore, ODTs avoid the first-pass metabolism, which enhances the bioavailability of the drug and reduces frequent administration of drugs⁹. ODTs are formulated using excipients such as film-forming polymers, plasticizers, superdisintegrants, and active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), making them a cost-effective dosage form. Superdisintegrants play a key role by breaking the tablet into smaller fragments, enabling rapid dissolution. Calcium channel blockers (CCBs) are used in the treatment of hypertension due to their vasodilatory effect, which reduces total peripheral resistance and, consequently, lowers blood pressure¹⁰. Research has shown that CCBs are as effective as other antihypertensive drugs in lowering blood pressure and may help prevent the onset of heart failure.¹¹

¹². Amlodipine besylate is a third-generation, long-acting dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker. It has an oral bioavailability of 60–65%, with peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) occurring approximately 6 to 8 hours after administration¹³. Amlodipine besylate is chemically described as (4R, S)-3-ethyl-5-methyl-2-(2-aminoethoxymethyl)-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-1,4-dihydro-6-methylpyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate monobenzene sulfonate. It is a third-generation dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker¹⁴. Amlodipine is a first-line agent for hypertension¹⁵ and angina pectoris¹⁶. Patient compliance is crucial for amlodipine besylate, especially in elderly, pediatric, and special-needs patients. It's available as oral tablets in 5 mg and 10 mg doses, with 6.9 mg of the besylate salt equivalent to 5 mg of amlodipine. Amlodipine is well absorbed (96%) with a bioavailability of 64–90%¹⁷. It belongs to the BCS class I drugs, making it easier to be manufactured as a mouth-dissolving tablet¹⁸.

Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents: Amlodipine Besylate (IPCA Laboratories, Mumbai, India; Stock solution Batch no. 22005AK5RH); Crospovidone, Magnesium Stearate, and Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG) (HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Maharashtra, India); Saccharin Sodium, PVP K-30, and Aerosil (Central Drug House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India); Mannitol (Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India).

2.2 Determination of λ_{max} of Amlodipine Besylate: To determine the wavelength of maximum absorption, the UV spectrum of amlodipine besylate was recorded using a Shimadzu UV-visible spectrometer. A stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of the drug in 100 mL of distilled water. Working solutions of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were made by diluting 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL, respectively. These solutions were scanned from 400 nm to 200 nm, and the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) was identified at 238 nm.

2.3 Preparation of standard calibration curve.

Solutions ranging from 0 to 30 µg/mL, in 5 µg/mL increments, were prepared. Absorbance for each solution was measured at 238 nm using distilled water as a blank with a Shimadzu UV spectrophotometer.

2.4 Drug excipients compatibility study by IR Spectroscopy. The drug and excipients were mixed in a 1:1 ratio and stored in a desiccator for 2 months. Afterward, they were analyzed for any degradation using infrared spectroscopy.

2.5 Analytical Method Validation

The parameters for analytical method validation are:

2.5.1 Linearity

To construct calibration curves and determine regression equations, amlodipine besylate solutions of various concentrations (10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/mL) were prepared. Their absorbance was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer and plotted with concentration on the X-axis and absorbance on the Y-axis. The calibration curve for amlodipine in the 10–30 µg/mL range is shown in Figure 1.

2.5.2 Accuracy

Accuracy was assessed at three concentrations of amlodipine—12 µg/mL, 15 µg/mL, and 18 µg/mL—representing 20% below, at, and 20% above the assay concentration. Each concentration was tested in triplicate using the assay method. Accuracy was calculated using the formula: Accuracy = [Analytical result/ True result] *100

2.5.3 Specificity

This was performed by measuring the absorbance of amlodipine besylate and all excipients used in the formulation at 238 nm.

2.6. Preparation of Amlodipine besylate ODTs.

The experimental design involved varying the concentrations of the superdisintegrants,

crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate (SSG), with levels selected based on guidelines from The Handbook of Excipients¹⁹. According to The Handbook of Excipients, sodium starch glycolate (SSG) is used at concentrations of 2–8%, while crospovidone is used at 2–5%. Based on this, eight formulations were prepared: F1, F2, F3, and F4 contained 2%, 4%, 6%, and 8% SSG, respectively; F5, F6, F7, and F8 contained 2%, 3%, 4%, and 5% crospovidone, respectively. All other ingredients remained constant across formulations. Amlodipine besylate, crospovidone, SSG, and mannitol were sieved through a #40 mesh and collected separately. Fast-disintegrating tablets (FDTs) were prepared using the direct compression method. The drug and diluents were mixed geometrically and blended for 20 minutes. The mixture was then lubricated with aerosil and magnesium stearate (sieved through #60 mesh) for 5 minutes. Finally, tablets were compressed using an 8 mm circular flat punch on a tablet compression machine.

2.7 Pre-compression parameters of the tablet

2.7.1 Bulk density

Bulk density is defined as the ratio of the total mass of a powder to its bulk (untapped) volume. It was determined by pouring 100 g of the powder blend into a graduated cylinder and recording the bulk volume (V_b). The bulk density (ρ_b) was then calculated using the formula:

$$\rho_b = M/V_b$$

Where,

M is the weight or mass of the powder

2.7.2 Tapped density

Tapped density is the ratio of the total mass of the powder to its tapped volume. To determine tapped density, 100 g of the powder blend was placed into a graduated cylinder, which was mechanically tapped 500 times to record the initial tapped volume. Tapping continued for a total of 750 taps, and the final tapped volume (V_t) was noted. The

tapped density (ρ_t) was calculated using the formula:

$$\rho_t = M/V_t$$

Where,

M is the mass or weight of the powder.

2.7.3 Carr's Index

Carr's index, named after Ralph J. Carr, Jr., indicates the compressibility of a powder. It is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{[\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk density}]}{\text{Tapped density}} * 100\%$$

2.7.4 Hausner ratio

The Hausner ratio, named after engineer Henry H. Hausner, indicates the flowability of a powder or granular material. It is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Hausner ratio (H)} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

2.7.5 Angle of Repose

The angle of repose is defined as the steepest angle relative to the horizontal plane at which a material can be piled without slumping. It was measured using the fixed funnel method. A 75 g powder blend was poured through a funnel fixed 10 cm above a flat surface. The diameter (d) and height (h) of the resulting powder heap were measured. The angle of repose (θ) was calculated using the formula:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (2h/d)$$

2.8 Post-compression Parameters of the tablet

2.8.1 Weight variation

Twenty tablets from each batch were weighed individually on an analytical balance, and the average values and deviation from the average value were calculated.

2.8.2 Thickness variation

Thickness variation was measured using a Vernier caliper on 10 tablets from each batch. The average thickness was calculated and reported as mean \pm SD.

2.8.3 Hardness

The hardness of 10 tablets from each batch was measured using a Labinda hardness tester. The average hardness was calculated and reported as mean \pm SD.

2.8.4 Friability

Tablets weighing approximately 6.5 g were tested for friability using a Roche friabilator at 25 rpm for 4 minutes (100 revolutions). After testing, the tablets were weighed, and the percentage weight loss was calculated.

$$\text{Friability (\%)} = \frac{(W_1 - W_2)}{W_1} * 100$$

Where,

W1 = Weight before a test

W2 = Weight after a test

2.8.5 Disintegration

One tablet was placed in each of six tubes in the basket assembly, which was then suspended in water maintained at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The apparatus was operated, and the time taken for all tablets to disintegrate was recorded.

2.9 Dissolution studies

2.9.1 Preparation of dissolution medium

0.1N Hydrochloric acid was used as a dissolution medium.

2.9.2 Method for dissolution

The release rate of amlodipine besylate from the fast-dissolving tablets was determined using the

previously described method. The dissolution study parameters were as follows:

- Dissolution medium: 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl.
- Dissolution apparatus: Paddle
- Rotating speed: 75 rpm
- Temperature: 37±0.5 degrees Celsius
- Time: 15sec, 30sec, 45sec, 60sec, 75sec.

2.9.3 Analysis of dissolution sample

Samples of 10 mL were withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at regular intervals (15, 30, 45, 60, and 75 seconds) and immediately replaced with an equal volume of fresh dissolution medium. The samples were filtered through filter paper, and their absorbance was measured at 238 nm using a Shimadzu UV/Vis spectrophotometer. The cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated and plotted graphically.

2.9.4 Assay [By UV-VIS spectrophotometer]

To measure the assay, 20 tablets were weighed and crushed using a mortar and pestle. Powder equivalent to 10 mg of amlodipine was dissolved in 100 mL of water to prepare a 100 µg/mL stock solution. This stock was diluted by taking 1 mL and making up the volume to 10 mL to obtain a 10 µg/mL working solution. The absorbance of this

solution was measured at 238 nm, and the assay was calculated by comparing the absorbance to the standard calibration curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development of Master Formula for Amlodipine Besylate Tablets

This tablet formulation aims to develop an optimal 10 mg amlodipine besylate direct compression tablet by varying the proportion of disintegrants while keeping other excipients constant. The primary goal is to evaluate the effects of sodium starch glycolate (SSG) and crospovidone on tablet disintegration and dissolution for effective ODT delivery. Formulations F1–F4 contain increasing amounts of SSG (2%–8%), which swells on water absorption to break the tablet apart, while F5–F8 have increasing crospovidone concentrations (2%–5%), promoting disintegration via capillary action. Other excipients remain unchanged: magnesium stearate as a lubricant, aerosil to improve flowability, saccharin sodium for taste masking, PVP K-30 as a binder, and mannitol as a filler to achieve a 200 mg tablet weight. The final formulation will be selected based on a comprehensive evaluation of hardness, friability, disintegration time, and dissolution profile to ensure optimal drug performance.

Table 1: Master Formula of the Formulation details the composition of eight Amlodipine Besylate tablet formulations with varying disintegrants and excipients.

S. No	Ingredients (mg/tablets)	F1 (mg)	F2 (mg)	F3 (mg)	F4 (mg)	F5 (mg)	F6 (mg)	F7 (mg)	F8 (mg)
1	Amlodipine Besylate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2	SSG (%)	2	4	6	8	-	-	-	-
3	Crospovidone	-	-	-	-	2	3	4	5
4	Magnesium Stearate (0.5%)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	Aerosil (1%)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
6	Saccharin sodium (1%)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
7	PVP-K30 (4%)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
8	Mannitol (QS)	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Pre and Post-Compression Evaluation Results of Tablet Formulations (F1 to F8)

Table 2 presents the results of pre-compression evaluation of the powder blends and post-compression evaluation of the amlodipine fast-disintegrating tablets (FDTs). Pre-compression

parameters indicated good free-flowing properties, with low Hausner's ratio, compressibility index, and angle of repose reflecting fair flowability. The tablets were free from defects such as chipping, sticking, capping, and lamination, and exhibited uniform weight with acceptable variation between 190 mg and 210 mg. Hardness values ranged from 3.0 to 3.3 kg/cm², and friability loss was less than 1%, indicating good mechanical strength and binding properties suitable for handling and transport. Drug content ranged from 102.7% to 109.6%, within the acceptable limit of 90% to 110%. Disintegration time, a critical parameter for FDTs, ranged from 18 to 65 seconds. Formulations containing sodium starch glycolate showed comparatively slower dissolution rates. The tablet with 5% crospovidone exhibited the fastest disintegration time of 18 seconds, while the one with 2% SSG had the longest disintegration time of 65 seconds. The shortest disintegration time of 18 seconds at a low concentration highlights crospovidone as a superior superdisintegrant

compared to sodium starch glycolate (SSG). This rapid disintegration is attributed to crospovidone's faster capillary action, swelling 4 to 10 times quicker than SSG²⁰. In this study, disintegration time decreased with increasing concentrations of superdisintegrants. These results suggest that higher superdisintegrant levels lead to faster tablet disintegration. Both sodium starch glycolate (SSG) and crospovidone met the criteria for fast-disintegrating tablets, disintegrating in under one minute within their respective concentration ranges². FDTs of amlodipine prepared by Krishna Mohan Pr et al (2010) using crospovidone and Sodium Starch Glycollate (at the concentration of 4%, 6% and 8%) also showed the disintegration time of less than 50 seconds^{21 22}. FDTs of amlodipine Besylate were also prepared using crospovidone and SSG, and the disintegration time of all the formulations was in the range of 22sec-35sec²². The researchers found the disintegration time of 10 seconds for all formulations²³.

Table 2: Comprehensive Pre- and Post-Compression Characterization of Tablet Formulations (F1 to F8), Including Physical and Performance Evaluation Parameters

Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Pre-compression evaluation								
Bulk density (g/mL)	0.45	0.44	0.47	0.43	0.44	0.44	0.45	0.46
Tapped density (g/mL)	0.53	0.57	0.55	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.56	0.54
Angle of repose (Θ)	30.60	29.11	29.72	29.53	30.02	30.09	29.84	29.93
Carr's index (%)	14	22	14.5	20	18.51	18.51	19.6	14.91
Hausner's ratio	1.17	1.29	1.17	1.25	1.22	1.22	1.22	1.17
Post-compression evaluation								
Hardness (kg/cm²)	3.06 ±0.14	3.09 ±0.13	3.22 ±0.07	3.1 ±0.09	3.19 ±0.08	3.03 % ± 0.09	3.1 ± 0.12	3.17± 0.13
Thickness (mm)	4.09±0.08	4.11±0.09	4.06±0.08	4.07±0.05	4.02±0.05	4.09±0.05	4.05±0.08	4.08± 0.09
Weight variation (%)	1.34 ± 1.78	2.24 ±0.26	2.53± 2.12	2.98±0.25	1.42± 1.55	2.83± 2.30	3.25 ± 1.89	1.5 ± 1.74
Friability (%)	0.76	0.89	0.80	0.87	0.61	0.57	0.92	0.81
Disintegration (sec)	65	45	30	20	59	46	31	18
Assay (%)	105.85	107.16	104.70	109.62	104.46	106.79	102.70	105.66

Analytical Method Validation Results for Linearity, Specificity, and Accuracy

Figure 1 shows the plot of absorbance versus drug concentration, with an R^2 value of 0.9999, confirming the method's excellent linearity ($R^2 > 0.99$). Specificity testing revealed minimal interference from excipients in the placebo solution, with only 1.55% interference—well below the acceptable limit of 2%—demonstrating that excipients do not significantly affect the

drug's absorbance measurement. Accuracy, evaluated at 80%, 100%, and 120% of the target drug concentration (Table 4), showed percent recoveries consistently within the acceptable range of 98% to 102%. Recovery ranged from 100.75% to 101.91% at 80%, 99.53% to 101.8% at 100%, and 99.61% to 100.94% at 120% concentration levels. Low standard deviation and relative standard deviation (both under 1%) further confirm the method's precision and reliability for accurately determining drug concentration.

Figure 1 shows a linear calibration curve, confirming the accuracy of the method.

Table 3: Results for Specificity

Test solution	Absorbance
Placebo (Excipients)	0.0046
Standard	0.3015

Sample	0.2958
Percentage interference	1.55%
Limit	NMT 2%

Table 3 confirms the method's specificity, with excipient interference well below the acceptable limit.

Concentration of drug	Actual concentration of drug (µg/ml)	Quantity found (µg/ml)	Percent recovery (%)	% Mean (n=9)	Standard Deviation (n=9)	Relative standard deviation (n=9)
80%	12	12.23	101.91	100.71	0.91	0.90
80%	12	12.09	100.75			
80%	12	12.15	101.25			
100%	15	15.27	101.8			
100%	15	14.93	99.53			
100%	15	14.95	99.66			
120%	18	18.17	100.94			
120%	18	17.93	99.61			
120%	18	18.11	100.94			

Table 4 confirms the method's accuracy, with recovery percentages within the acceptable range and minimal variation.

Comparison of Cumulative Drug Release Profiles for SSG and Crospovidone in Tablet Formulations
In vitro release studies showed that over 80% of the drug was released from all formulations within 75 seconds. Formulation F5 demonstrated the fastest drug release among them. Overall, crospovidone exhibited a higher dissolution rate compared to sodium starch glycolate. Other researchers have reported similar findings; for example, Krishna Mohan Pr et al. (2010) prepared amlodipine FDTs using crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate at concentrations of 4%, 6%, and

8%, observing dissolution profiles ranging from 74.33% to 96.78%. In their study, formulations containing sodium starch glycolate showed a comparatively higher dissolution rate than those with crospovidone, with the enhancement order being Sodium Starch Glycolate > Crospovidone²¹. However, in our case, crospovidone has a relatively higher dissolution rate than SSG. Previously, FDTs of amlodipine besylate were prepared using crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate as superdisintegrants. The dissolution profile of the formulations ranges from 77.84% - 87.55%²³. Similar to our result, the order of the dissolution rate was found to be crospovidone > Sodium starch glycolate.

Figure 1(a): Cumulative Drug Release Profile for SSG

Figure 2(b): Cumulative Drug Release Profile for Crosopvidone

CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate the promising potential of fast-disintegrating amlodipine tablets formulated by direct compression using a specific ratio of crosopvidone and sodium starch glycolate (SSG) as superdisintegrants. Among the batches tested, formulation F8 (containing 5% crosopvidone) showed the best performance in terms of friability, hardness, drug content uniformity, disintegration time, and in vitro drug release. Crosopvidone was found to be a superior disintegrant compared to SSG. Increasing the concentration of superdisintegrants enhanced drug release by accelerating tablet disintegration in the mouth, which may improve drug dissolution, absorption, and lead to a faster onset of action—beneficial for treating hypertension and coronary artery disease.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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REFERENCES

1. Ruiz ME, Scioli Montoto S. Routes of Drug Administration. ADME Process Pharm Sci Dosage, Des Pharmacother Success. Published online January 1, 2018:97-133. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-99593-9_6
2. Parkash V, Maan S, Deepika, Yadav S, Hemlata H, Jogpal V. Fast disintegrating tablets: Opportunity in drug delivery system. J Adv Pharm Technol Res. 2011;2(4):223-235. doi:10.4103/2231-4040.90877
3. Synthesis and biological evaluation of methotrexate analogues for anticancer activity | Request PDF. Accessed December 25, 2024. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256071112_Synthesis_and_biological_evaluation

- _of_methotrexate_analogues_for_anticancer_activity
4. Cantor SL, Khan MA, Gupta A. Development and optimization of taste-masked orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) of clindamycin hydrochloride. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 2015;41(7):1156-1164. doi:10.3109/03639045.2014.935392
 5. Agarwal DS, Misra R, Gautam DGK. FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF TASTE MASKING MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLETS OF LEVOCETRIZINE DIHYDROCHLORIDE. *Int J Pharma Prof Res.* 2023;14(1):47-58. Accessed December 28, 2024. <https://www.ijppronline.com/index.php/IJPPR/article/view/265>
 6. (PDF) ORODISPERSIBLE TABLETS: AN OVERVIEW OF FORMULATION AND TECHNOLOGY. Accessed December 28, 2024. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344557528_ORODISPERSIBLE_TABLETS_A_N_OVERVIEW_OF_FORMULATION_AND_TECHNOLOGY
 7. Wiedey R, Kokott M, Breikreutz J. Orodispersible tablets for pediatric drug delivery: current challenges and recent advances. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv.* 2021;18(12):1873-1890. doi:10.1080/17425247.2021.2011856
 8. Ghourichay MP, Kiaie SH, Nokhodchi A, Javadzadeh Y. Formulation and Quality Control of Orally Disintegrating Tablets (ODTs): Recent Advances and Perspectives. *Biomed Res Int.* 2021;2021. doi:10.1155/2021/6618934
 9. Shafi H, Rashid R, Rather S ullah, et al. Super disintegrating oromucosal nanofiber patch of zolmitriptan for rapid delivery and efficient brain targeting. *Chem Eng J.* 2023;463:142481. doi:10.1016/J.CEJ.2023.142481
 10. Tang L, Gamal El-Din TM, Lenaeus MJ, Zheng N, Catterall WA. Structural Basis for Diltiazem Block of a Voltage-Gated Ca²⁺ Channel. *Mol Pharmacol.* 2019;96(4):485-492. doi:10.1124/MOL.119.117531
 11. Zhu J, Chen N, Zhou M, et al. Calcium channel blockers versus other classes of drugs for hypertension. *Cochrane database Syst Rev.* 2022;1(1). doi:10.1002/14651858.CD003654.PUB6
 12. Jones KE, Hayden SL, Meyer HR, et al. The Evolving Role of Calcium Channel Blockers in Hypertension Management: Pharmacological and Clinical Considerations. *Curr Issues Mol Biol* 2024, Vol 46, Pages 6315-6327. 2024;46(7):6315-6327. doi:10.3390/CIMB46070377
 13. Meredith PA, Elliott HL. Clinical pharmacokinetics of amlodipine. *Clin Pharmacokinet.* 1992;22(1):22-31. doi:10.2165/00003088-199222010-00003
 14. Heidari H, Limouei-Khosrowshahi B. Magnetic solid phase extraction with carbon-coated Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coupled to HPLC-UV for the simultaneous determination of losartan, carvedilol, and amlodipine besylate in plasma samples. *J Chromatogr B.* 2019;1114-1115:24-30. doi:10.1016/J.JCHROMB.2019.03.025
 15. Fares H, DiNicolantonio JJ, O'Keefe JH, Lavie CJ. Amlodipine in hypertension: a first-line agent with efficacy for improving blood pressure and patient outcomes. *Open Hear.* 2016;3(2). doi:10.1136/OPENHRT-2016-000473
 16. Taylor SH. Usefulness of amlodipine for angina pectoris. *Am J Cardiol.* 1994;73(3). doi:10.1016/0002-9149(94)90271-2
 17. (PDF) Bioavailability File: Amlodipine. Accessed January 6, 2025.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260834619_Bioavailability_File_Amlodipine

18. Dhiman J, Dev D, Prasad DN. Superdisintegrants: Brief Review. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2022;12(1):170-175. doi:10.22270/JDDT.V12I1.5155
19. Covet M. Handbook of Pharmaceutical excipients. Accessed January 6, 2025. https://www.academia.edu/40798342/Handbook_of_Pharmaceutical_excipients
20. Markl D, Zeitler JA. A Review of Disintegration Mechanisms and Measurement Techniques. *Pharm Res.* 2017;34(5):890-917. doi:10.1007/S11095-017-2129-Z
21. Maheswari KM, Devineni PK, Deekonda S, Shaik S, Uppala NP, Nalluri BN. Development and Evaluation of Mouth Dissolving Films of Amlodipine Besylate for Enhanced Therapeutic Efficacy. *J Pharm.* 2014;2014:520949. doi:10.1155/2014/520949
22. View of FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING TABLET OF AMLODIPINE BESYLATE | International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics. Accessed December 25, 2024. <https://journals.innovareacademics.in/index.php/ijap/article/view/31288/20301>
23. Raj BS, Punitha ISR, Dube S. Formulation and Characterization of Fast Disintegrating tablets of Amlodipine using Super-disintegrants. *J Appl Pharm Sci.* 2012;2(8):118-123. doi:10.7324/JAPS.2012.2819.

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